

“A REVIEW OF PARIKARTIKA IN AYURVEDA”***¹Dr. Ketan Manik More, ²Dr. S. N. Patil, ³Dr. R. C. Yakkundi, ⁴Dr. K. H. Pachchinavar, ⁵Dr. Anju D. R.**¹1st Year PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalyatantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.²Professor, Dept. of Shalyatantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.³Professor & HOD, Dept. of Shalyatantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.⁴Professor, Dept. of Shalyatantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.⁵Assistance Professor, Dept. of Shalyatantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Ketan Manik More**1st Year PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalyatantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18084921>**How to cite this Article:** *1Dr. Ketan Manik More, 2Dr. S. N. Patil, 3Dr. R. C. Yakkundi, 4Dr. K. H. Pachchinavar, 5Dr. Anju D. R. (2026). A REVIEW OF PARIKARTIKA IN AYURVEDA. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(1), 86–89.

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Article Received on 22/11/2025

Article Revised on 12/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda science has mentioned various principles for maintaining proper health. Prevention is better than cure is one of the important Aim of Ayurveda.^[1] Fissure-in-ano is a very common and painful condition. Fissures occurs most commonly in the midline posteriorly, the least protected part of the anal canal.^[2] In Ayurveda, Fissure-in-ano can be correlated with the disease Parikartika. It is not mentioned as one of the separate disease in Ayurveda text. Parikartika described as one of the complication of Basti karma,^[3] also a Garbhini vyapada^[4] and Vamana-Virechana Vyapada.^[5] It also explained as one of the poorva roopa of Arsha vyadhi. Parikartika was presented with pain, burning sensation, constipation, etc. Ayurveda is an ancient medical science in which various treatment modalities are explained for Parikartika and other Anal disorders.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Parikartika, Fissure-in-Ano.**INTRODUCTION**

Description about Parikartika is also available in all Bruhatrayees and later classics. Parikartika is referred in Brihatrayees not as an independent disease but as a complication of Bastikarma and Virechana (vyapath). In Parikartikartika due to nidanas aggravated vata attains upward movement and repelled by udanavayu reaches Guda and obstructs the passage of feces producing severe pain, Gudadaha, pichha srava etc. From the available explanations in the classics, we can infer that Parikartika is a Vranalakshanayukta gudavikar and which is very much suggestive of the modern ailment Fissure in ano when it is limited to anal region.

Fissure-in-Ano is very commonly encountered problem in current day practice. It is very common in youngsters and women after child birth and about 30-40% of the population suffers from proctologic pathologies at least once in their lifetime. So there is an alarming rise in the incidence. Anal fissure comprises of 10-15% of all Ano-rectal disorders and is characterized by excruciating pain during and after defecation, bleeding per anum with

spasm of anal sphincters. Pain may be so severe that patient may avoid defecation for days until it becomes inevitable. This leads to hardening of the stools which further tear the anoderm during defecation, setting a vicious cycle.

Acute Fissure-in-Ano is most painful condition and generally it takes 2-3 weeks to heal even with the use of stool softeners and topical applications. Yet, some fissures persist for more than 6 weeks and considered as chronic ones which show reluctance to heal.

Review on Parikartika**Definition**

The term Parikartika is derived from Sanskrit word ‘Parikr, which denotes ‘all around’ all over” or “whole” or “every entity” or “every aspect” and ‘Kartanam’ or Kartika is derived from “Krita” verb, which means to cut. It means that excessive cutting pain in and around the anus is seen in Parikartika.^[6]

Synonyms

- Parkartika
 - Guda vidara
 - Guda Kshata
 - Kasta Guda
 - Kasta payu
 - Vyakta Mala
- Pain is the most important clinical symptoms in this disease.

Nirukti

It refers to a condition in which patient experiences a sensation of pain as if the Guda is being cut around with scissor. The disease is characterized by excessive cutting pain around the anus.^[6]

Kashyapa says that Parikartika is the one having cutting and tearing pain in guda pradesha. Jejjata has anticipated this condition and explained pin pointedly. According to him in Parikartika a specific pain i.e. a cutting and tearing pain around the anal region. Dalhana also gives the similar opinion.

Nidana

Proper descriptions about Nidana, Smaprapti and Rupa etc. are not available in any of the classical literatures at place under the heading Parikartika as the Acharyas have not given much emphasis to the condition as a separate disease condition.^[7] That might be the reason we don't find any direct references / descriptions about the aetiopathogenesis of the Parikartika. However one can find the nidana that produce condition Parikartika in scattered manner. As described in the Sarvaroga Nidana Adhyaya, those doshas that are in the Sanchaya avastha get to Prakopa avastha in presence of aetiological factors and produce the disease.^[8]

In Parikartika, Vata is the primary Dosha, as the Guda is the seat of Vata especially Apana Vayu. The vitiation factors Vata are Tikta, Ushna, Kashaya, Alpa Bhojana, Vegadharana, Udirana, excessive Shodhana therapy; diurnal and seasonal variations. The second predominant Dosha is Pitta and the factors vitiating it are Katu, Amla, Lavana, Ahara, Krodha; diurnal and seasonal variations.

Kapha Dosha, thought not predominantly present for triggering the condition, but still it plays a role many ways and its vitiating factors are Swadu, Amla, Lavana, Adhyasana, Sita, Guru Bhojana, Divaswapna and diurnal and seasonal variations. besides these three Doshas, Acharya Sushruta has mentioned the Rakta is the 4th Dosha. He also says that as Vayu unites with blood Vrana is formed. In Parikartika, Vrana produced is mostly Nija in origin and Acharya Charaka in Chikitasasthana Dwivraneeya Adhyaya has explained that when Doshas take site in Bahya Roga Marga, they produce Vrana likewise prakruptita Vata and Pitta especially are the causes of Parikartika.

Rupa

When Vikrita Vata gets localized in Guda it produces retention of faeces, urine and flatus, colic pain and flatulence and Sarkara (fecolith)^[9] and according to Sushruta there is a pain of sharp cutting nature in Guda^[10] and due to this constipation develops. Acharya Vagbhatta has also described same signs and symptom as described by Acharya Charaka and Sushruta.^[11] Vrana is an essential symptom of Parikartika which is having Deeraghakruti shape or Tripatakakruti and there may be discharge along with other features of Dusta Vrana.^[12]

The causative factors of specified doshas will lead to vitiation of Vata and Pitta and they travel downwards to guda. These doshas will increase pressure in guda pradesha and produces Vikruti to Rakta and Mamsa which leads to kshata and thus produces kartanavat vedana in guda pradesha. This condition is called as Parikartika.^[13]

Bheda

Acharya Charaka and Sushruta both have described two types of Doshas in Parikartika viz. Vata and Pitta. In almost all Ayurvedic texts, no detailed descriptions about classification of disease, its Samprapti and Symptomatology have been specified, but Acharya Kashyapa has described the involvement of all the three Doshas e.g. Vata, Pitta and Kapha in the Adhyaaya of Garbhini Chikitsa while giving the detailed Chikitsa of the disease Parikartika. This classification is chiefly emphasized on the character of pain, shooting, cutting or pricking pain in Vata predominance, burning pain in pitta and dull ache type in kapha predominance. Since it is a known fact that Kashyapa Samhita is incomplete work and it might be possible that he might have considered the Nidana Panchaka of Parikartika in detail in some of lost portion over a period, but later on given a brief description of it in relation to a Gravid woman.^[14]

Sadhya Asadhyata

Sadhyasadhya of a disease is decided by considering all the factors which are likely to influence the curability and incurability of a disease. It is essential to consider the Sadhyasadhya before administering any forms of Chikitsa (treatment) any type of Vrana can be cured easily, provided the patient is with good Satva, Mamsa Dhatu, and Agni and if he is in his younger age. Also Vrana occurs in Guda can be cured easily if a Vrana is left untreated, the Sadhyatva, as a consequence may lead to Yapyatva stage and finally leading to Asadhyatva stage.

Parikartika which affects the superficial layer of the Twak (Anal skin) is easily curable. Therefore it can be included in the Sadhyata group. If it affects the deeper layers, it shows reluctance to heal. Therefore it can be included in Krichrasadhya group. If it is associated with Kushta, Vishadushti and Srotasa, the healing of Vrana will be delayed. If parikartika is associated with Sanniruddha guda, it is considered as Yapyata.

Chikitsa

Parikartika as a disease has been considered very briefly by Sushruta and other successive authors. They have described the treatment of Parikartika in most brief manner. Kashyapa has mentioned its management according to Doshika predominance, others have not considered as Doshika type classification, but it is a fact that none of them has described surgical management, thereby showing that there was no need of surgery as the disease was completely cured by the use of medicinal preparations only, and they were satisfied with management. According to route of administration the medicines are divided into two categories.^[15]

1) Local

2) General

Local Treatment

This local treatment is nothing but only Basti Karma. Basti is prepared in Ghrita, Taila and milk with the help of other different drugs. Most of the drugs, which are used in Basti Karma, are VataShamaka, Varna Shodhan – Ropaka and Pittashamaka. There are three types of Bastis described by Sushruta and other Ayurvedic authors viz. Anuvasana Basti ii) Piccha Basti and iii) Sital Basti. Remedy consists in employing a piccha Basti with Yashtimadhu and Sesamum pasted together and dissolved in clarified butter and honey. And patient should be kept on Anuvasana Basti, (in cases of Pitta predominance) Basti should be employed with the cream of clarified butter and in case of Vata predominance with Taila cooked with Yashtimadhu Charaka has also advocated both of medicines which have been advocated by the Sushruta. He says Sheeta Basti consisting of drugs having Madhura and Kashaya properties (Piccha and Anuvasana Basti) prepared by Madhuyasti powder and Kwatha should be used. Kashyapa has also advised for the Anuvasana Basti. In this type of Basti the base is milk, oil or Ghrita these are either Vatashmaka or Pitta shamaka. In many compositions so many drugs have been used they have Vata and Pitta shamaka properties and Madhuyasti is many times used. Because it has property of cooling, Vata- pitta-Rakta shamaka and widely it has been advocated by Sushruta for treatment of traumatic wounds, Pittaja Vrana, Fractures, Bhagandara, Upadansa and ulcer etc. Both the Acharya Charaka and Sushruta have advocated piccha Basti with Madhuyasti, Madhu and Taila for treatment of Parikartika.

General Treatment

The oral preparation have many- fold objective some are used to correct the anorectal disorders other are used as laxative and few more as to correct the Agnidugti. They have advised drugs as the Tridosha shamaka. Sushruta has advised for cold water bath and milk for oral administration.

In this disease the main problem is that of constipation and pain only. If one corrects the constipation part of disease and alleviates the pain the disease may disappear

to a great extent within few days. Pain due to Vata and Pitta vitiation and constipation due to two reasons-

- 1) Habitual constipation
- 2) Due to fear of pain patient does not go for the defaecation.

Acharya Charaka has also written about the oral treatment in Parikartika and advised for only milk drinking. Acharya Charaka has also advised to take Amla Dravya because it has the property of Vatashamaka and increases the digestive fire.

CONCLUSION

Parikartika is a word which has been referred to in Brihatrayees not as an independent disease but considered mainly as a Vaidyakrita vyapath in bastinetra vyapath and in Virechana vyapath where pain being the predominant feature. Description of this condition is very much suggestive of the modern ailment Fissure-in-ano.

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